

Gesture Control Robot using Arduino

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ABSTRACT

According to the World Federation of the Deaf, only 10 percent of the world's Deaf population receives any education, and only 3 percent receives this education in sign language. Another problem these deaf and face is inability to communicate with a person who does not understand the sign language. This project aims to reduce these problems by presenting a Sign Language. The project uses a hepatic glove to acquire signals corresponding to various hand gestures. The glove is interfaced with robot using an Arduino. Accelerometers are used to measure the angular displacement of human hand motion .The accelerometer controls the movement of the robot. Device is made of mainly two parts, one is RF transmitter and another is RF receiver. The RF transmitter will transmit the signal according to the position of accelerometer attached on your hand and the RF receiver will receive the signal and make the robot move in respective direction.

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KEYWORDS: Arduino, Wireless, RF transmitter & RF receiver, hand gesture

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, robotics is a current growing technology in science sector. A number of universities in the world are developing new things in this field. Robotics is the new growing field, which will be of great use to society in the coming years. Though humans can be replaced by robots, they still need to be controlled by humans itself. Robots can be wired or wireless, both having a human controller. It provides help to deaf people. Several research works are going on to make the communication between such person and a machine. Recognition of a sign language is very important not only from the engineering point of view but also for its impact on the human society. A sign language translator can provide an opportunity for the deaf people to live a normal life, there has not been any system with these capabilities so far. We have developed this project with an aim to help the deaf people so that they can live a normal life like others. Block diagram of a robot is shown in a figure 1.1. This project consists of two parts namely: (i) RF transmitter (ii) RF receiver.

Figure1.1: Block Diagram of Robot

The circuit diagram of the transmitter module is shown in figure 1.2 and the transmitter section consists of one Arduino Uno, one accelerometer and one RF transmitter module. The circuit diagram of the receiver module is shown in figure 1.3 and the receiver section consists of one RF receiver module, one motor driver IC, two PMDC motor, 4 wheels. Here ,two separate 5 volt power supply is applied to both the sections. Finally, Arduino Uno reads the analog output values i.e., x-axis and y-axis values from the accelerometer and converts analog value to respective digital value. The digital standards are processed by the Arduino Uno and transmit to the RF transmitter which is received by the Receiver and is processed at the receiver end which drives the robot to a particular direction. The robot moves forward, backward, right and left when there is tilt in the palm of user in forward, backward, right and left respectively.

chip there are two h-Bridge circuit within the IC which can turn two dc motor independently. Due to its small size it is very much used in robotic application for controlling DC motors.

3.4. DC Motor

DC motor is used to change direct current into mechanical motion. The motion could be rotary or linear. The operation of DC motor is depended on the principle that when a current carrying conductor is placed in a magnetic field, the conductor experiences a mechanical force. The speed of a DC motor can be controlled by varying the voltage applied to the armature or by varying the field current. DC motor can be used for the movement of the robotic system.

3.5. Battery

A battery is a electric tool made of one or more electrochemical cells. A battery is device that directly converts chemical energy into the electrical energy. The principle of battery is to supply 12 volts to operate DC motors.

3.6. RF Transmitter & Receiver

The transmitter section is working on the frequency of 433MHz. In the circuit, Vcc pin is connected to the + terminal and data pin is connected to the HT12E (Encoder) that is transmitted or we can say that encoded data. The next pin is GND that is linked to the ground terminal. Now the last pin ANT this is linked to a small wire as an antenna. The RF receiver will get the data which is transferred by the gesture device. It is also working as similar to the transmitter module- attach the +Vcc pin to the 5volt terminal. link the ground pin to the ground terminal .The data pin is then linked to the HT12D (Decoder) .So that we can get the decoded 4 bit data.

3.7. Camera

An image acquiring device which provides the video required for vision. In this project, we are using mi wireless camera.

4. Conclusion

Radio frequency transmission is used instead of infrared transmission as RF can travel longer distance which improves the range of application, RF can even work in obstruction between remotes and car. The RF module has a range of 20-

30 meters. This robot can be modify to detect human life in earthquake and landslide by implementing the sensor accordingly. It can also be used to bomb detecting robot. GPS system can be add to the robot by the help of which its location can be tracked.

5. Future scope

In the receiver section a wireless camera is placed to check the performance of robot. The on board batteries use a lot of space and are also quite heavy. We can either use some alternate power for the batteries or replace the DC Motors with ones which use less power. Most videogames are played either on game consoles or PCs, and all require a mixture of input devices. Gesture recognition can be used to truly engage a player in the game world like never before. In homes, offices, vehicles and more, gesture controlling can be combined to greatly increase usability and decrease the resources required to create primary or secondary input systems like remote controls, car entertainment systems with buttons or similar.

Reference

- [1] Premangshu Chanda, PallabKanti Mukherjee, SubrataModak, AsokeNath, "Gesture Controlled Robot using Arduino and Android", IJARCSSE, Volume 6, Issue 6, June 2016.
- [2] P. V. Patil, M. B. Shete, T. M. Padalkar, "Wireless Hand Gesture Robot using Accelerometer, Volume: 03 Issue: 04 , Apr-2016.
- [3] Saurabh A. Khajone, Dr. S. W. Mohod, V.M.Harne "Implementation of a Wireless Gesture Controlled Robotic Arm" in IJIRCCE Vol. 3, Issue 1, January 2015.
- [4] Vivek Bhojak, Girish Kumar Solanki, Sonu Daultani "Gesture Controlled Mobile Robotic Arm Using Accelerometer" in IJIRSET Vol. 4, Issue 6, June 2015.
- [5] SwarnaPrabha Jena, Sworaj Kumar Nayak, Saroj Kumar Sahoo, Sibur Ranjan Sahoo, Saraswata Dash, Sunil Kumar Sahoo, "Accelerometer Based Gesture Controlled Robot Using Aurdino" IJESRT.
- [6] Archika Setia, Surbhi Mittal, Padmini Nigam, Shalini Singh, Surendra Gangwar "Hand Gesture Recognition Based Robot Using Accelerometer Sensor" in IJAREEIE in Vol. 4, Issue 5, May 2015